

Application of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) on the Evolution of Mobile Edge Computing

Rabi Mustapha*

Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Kaduna State University P.M.B 2339, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author: rabichubu@kasu.edu.ng

Abstract

Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) has emerged as a promising paradigm that brings computation, storage, and intelligence closer to the network edge, enabling low-latency and high-bandwidth services. However, as MEC systems become increasingly complex, the need for Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques. The techniques arises to enhance transparency, interpretability, and trustworthiness. Tremendous success in machine learning has led to a novel trend of AI applications for example in transportation, security, medicine, finance, and defense that offer tremendous benefits but cannot explain their decisions and actions to human users. This article explores the application of XAI methods in the evolution of MEC, aiming to look into the evolution and the current trend of XAI to aid academia and researchers in the related field in decision-making processes within MEC systems.

Keywords: Mobile Edge Computing, Explainable Artificial Intelligence, XAI, Cloudlets, Cloud Computing, Fog Computing, Evolution.

1. Introduction

Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) has gained significant attention in recent years due to its potential to provide real-time and resource-efficient computation, storage, and intelligence at the network edge (Mach & Becvar, 2017). The integration of edge computing with artificial intelligence (AI) techniques has paved the way for a wide range of innovative applications and services (Wang et al., 2020). However, the inherent complexity of AI algorithms and the lack of transparency in their decision-making processes pose challenges for the adoption and trustworthiness of MEC systems. To mitigate these challenges, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques offer a solution by providing interpretable and understandable explanations for AI-driven decisions (Javed et al., 2023).

There are over two billion smartphones in the world today and the advent of the Internet of Things would see to the addition of many more billions of smart devices into the communication ecosystem. By some estimates smart devices would number up to 20 billion by the year 2020 (Gubbi, et al., 2013). The direct consequence of this proliferation of smart devices is the

overstretching of mobile networks and the internet backbone itself. This becomes even more pertinent with Big Data and the computation intensive applications that handle such data because mobile devices have major limitations in terms of computational capacity, battery life, and storage space. Because of these constraints, smart devices make extensive use of the Cloud to offload computation-intensive tasks. In spite of the apparent advantages of offloading onto the Cloud, there is an associated cost in terms of latency and Quality of Service. The time it takes for data to travel to the core of the network where Cloud servers are located and back is usually too long to make the execution of real-time applications feasible (Pavel & Zdenic, 2017). This forms the core of the argument for shifting computational power from the core of the network to the edge. Hence the birth of Edge Computing

2. Evolution of Mobile Edge Computing: Edge computing is a concept similar to distributed cloud computing. Edge computing is distributed computing system. It works by distributing the work of the device to the edge node near the physical distance as well as the cloud.

The widening gap between the demand for complex applications that require high computational capacity and huge storage space such as video processing, object recognition, or 3D navigation systems, and the availability of these resources in mobile devices have created a niche for Mobile Cloud Computing. Mobile Cloud Computing is a technology that is based on the idea of offloading complex applications that demand huge resources (in terms of computation and storage) to Cloud servers that have an abundance of these resources.

Offloading, as argued by Kumar et al. (2021), is different from other similar computing architectures like Client/Server or Grid computing. In both Client/Server and Grid Computing process migration occurs typically within the same computing environment – the Grid for Grid computing and the Local Area Network for Client/Server. Computational Offloading on the other hand involves migrating programs to servers outside of the immediate computing environment.

Figure 1. Architecture of Mobile Cloud Computing.

The figure 1 shows the typical architecture of Mobile Cloud Computing. Mobile user equipment connect to the Mobile network via base stations and subsequently use the internet infrastructure to connect to Cloud Servers through Cloud Service Providers.

This architecture however has a lot of latency inherent in it. This is largely due to the fact that it is WAN dependent and delay and jitter are parameters that are difficult to control in WANs (Pavel & Zdenic, 2017). An early solution to the issue of latency in Mobile Cloud Computing is the concept of Cloudlets.

(I) Cloudlets

Cloudlets are viewed as an implementation of Mobile Cloud Computing but conceptually they are more similar to Mobile Edge Computing (MEC). The difference being that in MEC servers are owned and managed by mobile infrastructure providers while Cloudlets are owned and managed by end-users (Beck, 2014).

Cloudlets are perhaps the first step in the evolution towards Mobile Edge Computing. Basically a Cloudlet is just a high capacity computer (or cluster of computers) that is deployed within the vicinity of mobile devices in order to provide computation and storage services to mobile user equipment (Pavel, & Zdenic, 2017). The Cloudlet is usually a single hop away from User Equipment and resource demanding applications can be offloaded and results sent back at incredibly low latencies.

The design architecture of Cloudlets is such that mobile devices switch from mobile networks to WIFI in order to access the Cloudlet services (Beck, 2014).

The major improvement that Cloudlets brought over the concept of Mobile Cloud Computing is in the reduction of latency. Latency hurts usability by degrading the crispness of system response thereby making deeply immersive and computation intensive tasks jerky to the point of distraction (Satyanarayanan, 2009).

A cloudlet typically has a 3-layered architecture; the component level, the node level and the cloudlet level (Verbelen, 2012). They also classified Cloudlets as adhoc and elastic. With adhoc Cloudlets, nodes are discovered dynamically as opposed to elastic Cloudlets whose entire infrastructure is visualized using a virtual machine.

(II) Fog Computing

In spite of the apparent advantages of MCC and Cloudlets, they still do not meet the needs of some mobile devices especially IoT. This is due to the fact that IoT applications usually require in addition to low latency, mobility support, geo-distribution, and location-awareness (Yi et al., 2015).

Fog computing is proposed to enable computing directly at the edge of the network, those devices that provide these services are called Fog nodes (Yi et al., 2015). Unlike in Cloudlets, Fog nodes do not have to be resource rich (Willis et al., 2014) because conceptually, fog nodes are a huge

number of heterogeneous (wireless and sometimes autonomous) ubiquitous and decentralized devices communicate and potentially cooperate among them and with the network to perform storage and processing tasks without the intervention of third parties Yi et al.(2015).

(III) Mobile Edge Computing

Basically, Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) is a computing paradigm in which the vast amounts of idle computation power and storage space distributed at network edges is harnessed in such a way that resource-constrained mobile devices can perform computation-intensive and latency-critical tasks Mao, et al. (2017). This paper discussed the application of XAI techniques in MEC enables improved transparency and interpretability in AI-driven decision-making processes.

(IV) Explainable Artificial intelligence (XAI): According to Das and Rad (2020) it is a field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that promotes a set of tools, techniques, and algorithms that can generate high-quality interpretable, intuitive, human-understandable explanations of AI decisions. The purpose of an explainable AI (XAI) system is to make its behavior more intelligible to humans by providing explanations (Gunning, et al. 2019).

The term was first coined in 2004 by Van Lent *et al.* to describe the ability of their system to explain the behavior of AI-controlled entities in simulation games application. While the term is relatively new, the problem of explainability has existed since the mid-1970s when researchers studied explanation for expert systems Moore, and Swartout (1988). However, the pace of progress towards resolving such problem has slowed down as AI reached an enunciation point with the spectacular advances in ML. Since then the focus of AI research has shifted towards implementing models and algorithms that emphasizes predictive power while the ability to explain decision processes has taken a back seat (Adadi & Berrada, 2018).

However, the study of Javed et al. (2023) define XAI as a method that helps humans comprehend how the output is created by the machine/deep learning algorithm. It contributes to quantifying model correctness, fairness, and transparency and results in AI-assisted decision-making. XAI is critical for organizations' trust and confidence when using AI models.

Figure 2 shows the dissimilarity between the working methodology of AI and XAI. As AI becomes more complex, humans face difficulty understanding and reviewing the algorithm's steps. The entire calculating process is transformed into what is often referred to as a "black box" that is impassable. These black-box models are constructed using the data directly, and not even the algorithm's developers or data scientists understand or can describe what is occurring inside them or how the AI algorithm arrived at a particular deduction (Rai, 2020).

Figure 2. Difference between the working methodology of AI and XAI adapted from Javed et al. (2023).

Lately, XAI area has received new attention from academia and practitioners. Figure 3, illustrates the remarkable rebirth of XAI in term of research interest using google trends.

Interest over time for AI term.

Figure 3. Google trends result for research interest of XAI term adapted from Adadi and Berrada (2018).

3. Methods: This article reviews the existing literature on the application of XAI methods in the context of MEC. It explores various XAI techniques, including rule-based models, feature importance analysis, model-agnostic approaches, and post-hoc explanation methods. The article also investigates the potential integration of XAI methods with MEC architectures, such as fog computing, and edge intelligence platforms. It shows the difference between the working

methodology of AI and XAI and also show the remarkable rebirth of XAI in term of research interest using google trends.

4. Results and Discussion: The application of XAI techniques in MEC enables improved transparency and interpretability in AI-driven decision-making processes. By generating human-understandable explanations for decisions made by MEC systems, XAI methods facilitate trust-building and enhance user acceptance. Moreover, XAI techniques can aid in identifying biases, errors, and vulnerabilities in MEC algorithms, contributing to system robustness and fairness.

The integration of XAI methods in MEC introduces a new perspective on the evolution of edge computing. By providing understandable explanations for AI-driven decisions, XAI bridges the gap between complex algorithms and end-users, enabling them to comprehend the decision-making processes and fostering trust. Furthermore, the combination of XAI and MEC can lead to enhanced resource allocation, intelligent workload distribution, and efficient utilization of edge computing resources.

5. Conclusion: The application of Explainable Artificial Intelligence techniques in the evolution of Mobile Edge Computing holds significant promise for addressing the challenges related to transparency, interpretability, and trustworthiness. Through the integration of XAI methods with MEC architectures, such as fog computing and edge intelligence platforms, the decision-making processes become more transparent and understandable, facilitating user acceptance and system reliability. Future research should focus on developing standardized XAI frameworks tailored for MEC, evaluating the performance of XAI algorithms in real-world MEC deployments, and exploring novel approaches to enhance the interpretability of complex AI models within the edge computing environment. Current research trend in XAI evaluation shows that the field of XAI is still evolving and that XAI methods should be developed and chosen with care. The future work of this study will look into the application of XAI in educational system of Nigerian institutions of higher learning (Universities) with particular emphasis on Kaduna State University (KASU). This can be done to improve safety; improve resource management; personalized student services and also to achieve smart infrastructure in the institutions of higher learning in the country.

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